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Development and Field Evaluation of Integrated Thermal Storage Double Exposure Box-type Solar Cooking System

¹N. S. Jega; ²M. M. Garba; ³B. S. Hamza & ⁴I. G. Saidu

¹Adamu Augie College of Education, Argungu, Kebbi State, Nigeria

²Sokoto Energy Research Center, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria

^{3,4}Physics Department Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Nigeria

Corresponding authors Email: nuhusanijega66@gmail.com

Phone Number: 08032953699

ABSTRACT

One major drawback of the box-type solar cookers is their inability to function when there is no sunlight. Some phase change materials (PCM) have been suggested to serve as heat reservoirs. Most of the materials currently in use as PCMs are scarce, costly or even poisonous. Shea butter oil and cow fat are two materials that are readily available in Kebbi State of Nigeria. This research focused on the development and field evaluation of an integrated thermal storage double exposure box-type solar cooking systems. Two cookers were designed and constructed using local materials. A parabolic reflector was used to direct solar radiation onto the lower sides of each of the cookers absorber plates, while plane mirrors further directed the radiation onto the top sides of each of the cookers. Both the top and the bottom of the cookers were covered with plain glasses exposed to transmit solar radiation. An integrated thermal storage compartment was attached to the collector. The first stagnation tests carried out for the two cookers without PCM yielded first figures of merit (F1) of 0.18 for both cookers. The maximum plate temperatures of 151 °C and 150 °C were attained for cooker A and B respectively, when the irradiance was 900W/m². The second stagnation tests carried out with PCM included (Shea butter for cooker A and cow fat for cooker B) yielded 0.15 and 0.16 as figures of merits for cooker A and cooker B respectively and a corresponding plate temperatures of 133 °C and 136 °C at irradiance of 910 W/m². It was concluded that the cookers fall into grade B category of cookers and that the additions of phase change material tend to lower the maximum temperature attained by the cookers as part of the heat is transferred to the PCMs.

Key words: Cow fat, figure of merit, PCM, Shea butter, solar cooker, stagnation test, Absorber plate

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Solar energy has served as the main source of energy that has sustained life on earth. Before the discovery of fire by human beings food was consumed mostly in its natural form (Khalifa *et al.*, 2000). The only means of food preparation or preservation was through solar drying. The discovery of fire enabled mankind to cook and preserve food more conveniently. Cooking with fire requires the consumption of mostly nonrenewable materials such as firewood, gas etc. nonrenewable energy sources are however

problematic as they are neither green nor renewable (Khalifa *et al.*, 2000). If mankind must survive in this energy craving world, alternative sources must be sort. Promising alternatives include wind, hydro and solar. Solar energy however has the advantage of being abundant, cheap and green.

The amount of solar irradiance reaching a particular location on earth is a function of the geographical location. Tropical regions such as Nigeria are known to receive favorable per unit solar irradiance. Hoase de Saussure, a Swiss naturalist, is credited for being the first inventor of a box for solar food cooking (Hebbar *et al.*, 2021). He cooked fruits in a primitive solar box cooker that reached a temperature of 190 °F. He is regarded as the grandfather of solar cooking. In 1837, a solar oven was invented by John Herschell. It was a black box that was insulated by burying it under the earth with only two glass covers on top that allowed sunlight to penetrate. In this box, food and vegetables were cooked to a temperature of 116 °C (Loff, 1963). The 1950s saw the beginning of the evolution of modern cookers. Numerous studies were embarked upon by the United Nations (UN) and other organizations to develop solar cookers that could reduce the demand on plants for fuel (Khalifa *et al.*, 2000).

Research and development on several kinds of solar cookers have been going on in Nigeria especially in institutions and research organizations. One of these organizations is the Sokoto Energy Research Centre cited at Usamanu Danfodiyo University, (UDU) Sokoto. Since its inception, in 1983, the center has been in the forefront in the novel development of different solar cookers (Sambo, 1990). These include solar hot box, solar concrete hot box, and cookers with two or all sides having reflecting boosters.

The adoption of new alternative energy techniques as compared to fossil fuels and firewood based cooking facilities are necessitated by economic and environmental considerations (Grupp *et al.*, 1991). Climate conditions, availability and affordability of traditional flues are a few of the factors taken into considerations when embarking on cooking systems (Loff, 2005). There are two types of solar cookers: box type and concentrating type of cookers (Loff, 2005). In the concentrating type of cookers a paraboloid reflecting surface is used to concentrate radiation to almost a point. The cooking vessel is normally positioned where the paraboloid reflection is strongest to receive- concentrated heat. As a result, temperatures beyond 200 °C can be reached and cooking times are significantly shortened (Loff, 2005). The simplest gadget for gathering solar thermal energy is the box-type cooker. The box type cooker has straightforward design, minimal construction costs, and no tracking requirements (Amer, 2002). A unique design for a box solar cooker was introduced by (Grupp *et al.*, in 1991). This cooker features a fixed cooking vessel that is in good thermal contact with a conductive absorber panel. Water has been brought to a boil using the cooker. The performance of a solar cooking oven that gathers solar energy and stores it in phase-change materials inside a heat exchanger has been reported by (Brushnell *et al.*, 1992). Several solar ovens have been reported from Indonesia (Suharat *et al.*, 2000). It has been reported that temperatures in the oven as high as 175 °C have been obtained, demonstrating the effectiveness of solar ovens for cooking (Suhara *et al.*, 2000). Due to the exponential growth in global energy demand, there will undoubtedly be an increase in the usage of fossil fuels, which will lead to numerous environmental issues such air pollution and climate changes (Abdulateef *et al.*, 2018). One clean, renewable and sustainable energy source that can assist in solving the problem is solar energy. The unavailability of solar energy supply in the nights, on the other hand, is a significant disadvantage that may be mitigated by creative thermal energy storage (TES) system designs (Khodadadi *et al.*, 2007). Phase change materials (PCMs) are used in latent thermal energy storage (LTES), a popular form of heat storage technology. LTES systems are frequently employed in solar-powered devices, like home solar hot water systems, to store and save extra energy during the sun's strongest hours. The extraordinary capacity of PCMs to store and release thermal energy during phase transitions has led to their extensive applications (Cuce *et al.*, 2013).

Limitations on fuel sources and CO₂ emissions are two worldwide problems that solar cookers have the ability to resolve. Therefore, further research projects are required to effectively develop and market solar cookers as a competitive alternative to the conventional cooking methods. Utilizing solar cookers could benefit the environment by lowering CO₂ emissions and assisting to decrease the current overreliance on fossil fuels. Together with the requirements for cost and performance, certain social criteria must also be

met for the product to be completely marketed and extensively used (Cuce *et al.*, 2013). In order to get beyond the restrictions and be able to utilize solar energy during hours when the sun isn't shining, solar cookers must be able to retain heat. To guarantee that solar cookers are feasible and marketable for usage in the future, research and promotional initiatives in the PCM field are necessary (Yettou, *et al.*, 2014). According to Schwartz *et al.*, (2003), thermal storage integrated cooking units contribute to a greater working fluid temperature and prolonged food warming. Schwartz *et al.*, (2003), used twelve cylindrical copper tubes that were directly exposed to solar rays and were loaded with various thermal storage materials. The tubes were then put inside the SBC, allowing the temperature to rise with natural convection. According to Saxena *et al.*, (2020), conduction came from the absorber plate and the sidewalls. A number of PCM-related issues were examined and evaluated, and the resolution offered by employing PCM to boost solar energy usage in research projects by reducing heat losses, enhancing heat transfer rate, and improving solar thermal system storage (Saxena *et al.*, 2020). Omara *et al.*, (2020) examined the performance of solar cookers using PCMs, which might increase the SC's overall usage efficiency by 85% and shorten its heating time by up to 15%. Through study, a unique design for a zero-emission cooking appliance utilizing an evacuated tube-based SCS is created and tested Omara *et al.*, (2020). By cutting down on cooking time, the evacuated glass tube reduces heat loss to the surrounding air. Heat transmission from the evacuated tube solar collector by thermo siphon cyclic effect heat transfer to the PCM-based cooking unit and subsequently employed for cooking accomplished by using heat transfer fluid (HTF) (Hebbar *et al.*, 2021). A country's ability to prosper rests on its ability to obtain affordable and plentiful energy (Cuce *et al.*, 2013). Every element of socioeconomic existence is greatly impacted by energy since it is essential to a country's survival and welfare development (Cuce *et al.*, 2013) (Buddhi *et al.*, 1999).

2.1 Materials (the materials used for the construction of the cookers are tabulated in Table 1).

Table 1: Materials, Components and Specifications

COMPONENTS	COOKER A Materials / Specifications	COOKER B Materials / Specifications
<u>Outer box</u>		
Material	MDF wood	MDF wood
Thickness	1.3cm	1.3cm
Dimensions (outer box)	66cm by 56cm	66cm by 56cm
Dimensions (inner)	64cm by 54cm	64cm by 54cm
Dimensions (bottom)	64cm by 54cm	64cm by 54cm
<u>Metal box</u>		
Material	Galvanized iron sheet	Galvanized iron sheet
Thickness	0.5mm	0.5mm
Aperture area	0.345m ²	0.345m ²
Dimensions	64cm by 54cm	64cm by 54cm
Coating	Black	Black
<u>Parabolic reflector</u>		
Type	Plane mirror	Plane mirror
Thickness	4mm	4mm
Dimensions	66cm by 75cm	66cm by 75cm
<u>Glass cover</u>		
Type (inner/outer)	Plain Glass	Plain Glass
Number	2	2
Dimension	66cm by 55cm	65cm by 55cm
Thickness	4mm	4mm
Spacing	3cm	3cm
<u>Plane reflector</u>		
Type	Plane mirror	Plane mirror
Thickness	4mm	4mm
Dimensions	65cm by 55cm	65cm by 55cm
<u>Cooker stand</u>		
Material	Angle iron	Angle iron
Thickness	3mm	3mm
Length	100cm	100cm
<u>Pivoted adjusting bar</u>		
Material	Metal bar	Metal bar
Dimensions	40cm by 2cm	40cm by 2cm
<u>PIPES</u>		
<u>Material</u>	Galvanized pipe	Galvanized pipe
<u>size</u>	1.5cm radius	1.5cm radius
<u>Shea Butter Oil Volume</u>	1Litre	
<u>Cow Fat Oil Volume</u>		1Liter

Plate 1: The complete assembly of one of the cookers

2.2 Methodology (Description and Construction of Double Exposure Box-Type Solar Cookers - DEBSC)

Two identical double exposure box-type solar cookers (DEBSC) were designed and constructed using locally available materials. The main considerations for material selection included: local availability, low cost, ease of handling during fabrication, lightweight for portability, durability under environmental and operational conditions, and non-toxic properties. The absorber plate was fabricated from commercially available galvanized iron (GI), painted black to enhance its absorptivity. GI was chosen due to its good thermal conductivity and high resistance to corrosion (Funk *et al.*, 1998). Although copper would provide superior thermal properties, it was considered unsuitable because of its high cost and limited availability. For glazing, a 4 mm thick glass sheet was used. The glass was commercially available and possessed desirable cover properties: high optical transmittance, low reflectivity, low heat transmittance, and minimal solar absorptance (Grupp *et al.*, 1991). Insulation was provided using cotton wool and Styrofoam, both of which are inexpensive, readily available, have low thermal conductivity, and remain stable at the operating temperature ranges. The casing was constructed with medium density fiber board (MDF) wood, 1.3 cm thick. MDF was selected because it is lightweight, rigid, easy to handle during construction, inexpensive, and widely available.

The unique feature of the DEBSC is the double glazing both at the top and bottom allowing the absorber plate to receive solar radiation simultaneously from both directions. Booster reflectors were incorporated: a plain mirror at the top and a parabolic mirror at the bottom. These mirrors increased solar radiation concentration on the absorber plate.

Integrated PCM compartments were fabricated from galvanized pipes and attached directly to the absorber plate's aperture area. The PCMs stored excess heat during peak sunlight hours and released it during non-sunlight periods, thereby enabling extended cooking and food warming. Each PCM compartment had inlet and outlet provisions for easy filling and discharging. A support stand, constructed from 100 cm angle iron, was built to hold the cooker securely. Two (2) aluminium cooking pots, painted black (30 cm in diameter and 15 cm in height), were used for performance evaluation. The plain booster mirror was made from a commercially available specular mirror with high optical reflectivity. A photograph of the constructed double exposure solar cooker is presented in Plate 1.

2.3. Performance Evaluation of the Cookers (Stagnation test for Cooker A and B without Heat Storage Media (PCM))

After the constructions, the two identical cookers were tested on 22/2/2024 at the testing ground of Sokoto Energy Research Centre, UDUS (13°4 latitude and 5°13' longitude) using the established standard methods to determine their first figures of merit. To do this, stagnation tests were conducted for the cookers first without storage media and then with storage. The two cookers were exposed to solar radiation at the same time under same prevailing weather conditions and were extensively tested as per IS 13429 (part3)1999 code of testing (Anon, 2006). The stagnation temperature test was carried out to determine the first figures of merit (F₁). The empty cookers were placed on a horizontal surface at the same time for measurement of stagnation temperatures. During this test, absorber plate temperature, ambient temperature, wind speed and oven air temperatures were also recorded after every 20 minutes using a digital thermometer and an anemometer respectively. The corresponding solar radiation values were also measured in each case. The first figure of merit (F₁) was determined using equation 1

$$F_1 = \frac{T_{PA,max} - T_{Aav}}{G_{SAV}} \quad (1)$$

Where T_{PA}, T_A and G_s are respectively, the absorber plate temperature, the average ambient temperature and the average solar radiation on a horizontal surface at the time stagnation temperature is reached.

2.4 Stagnation test for cooker A and B with Heat Storage Media (PCM).

The two cookers were exposed to solar radiation under similar weather conditions. Cooker A contains one liter of Shea butter oil and cooker B contains one liter of Cow fat oil as PCM in the heat storage pipes. Temperature sensors were inserted into the oils within the cookers to measure the temperatures. Solar radiation data were collected using a Pyranometer. Other ambient parameters (wind speed, ambient temperature and solar irradiance) during experiments were also measured.

The temperature readings were recorded at regular intervals of 20 minutes throughout the test. The thermal performance of the two storage media were evaluated based on parameters such as the maximum plate temperature reached, oven air temperature, Shea butter temperature and cow fat temperatures. The collected data were tabulated, analyzed and the thermal performances of the two heat storage media were compared. The effectiveness of each medium in reaching and maintaining the desired stagnation temperature were assessed. The Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) model was used to estimate the first figures of merit using equation (1).

3.1 Results (Stagnation Test Result for Cooker A without PCM)

Stagnation Temperature Test Result of Cooker A without PCM is presented in figure 3.1

Figure 3.1 Stagnation Temperature Test Result of Cooker A without PCM Conducted on 22/02/2024

Results from figure 3.1 is used to find the first figure of merit F1 for cooker A without PCM using equation (1) and it was found to be 0.18.

3.2 Stagnation Test Result for Cooker B without PCM

Stagnation Temperature Test Result for Cooker B without PCM is presented in figure 3.2

Figure 3.2 Stagnation Temperature Test Result of Cooker B without PCM Conducted on 22/02/2024.

Results from figure 3.2 is used to find the first figure of merit F1 for cooker B without PCM using equation (1) and it was found to be 0.18.

3.3 Stagnation Temperature Test Result for Cooker A with Shea butter as PCM

Stagnation Temperature Test Result for shea butter cooker is presented in figure 3.3

Figure 3.3 Stagnation Temperature Test Result for Cooker A with Shea butter as PCM conducted on 23/02/2024.

Results from figure 3.3 is used to find the first figure of merit F1 for shea butter cooker using equation (1) and it was found to be 0.15.

3.4 Stagnation Temperature Test Result for Cooker B with Cow fat as PCM

Stagnation Temperature Test Result for Cooker B with Cow fat as PCM is presented in figure 3.4

Figure 3.4 Stagnation Temperature Test Result for Cooker B with Cow fat as PCM Conducted on 23/02/2024.

Results from figure 3.4 is used to find the first figure of merit F1 for cow fzt cooker using equation (1) and it was found to be 0.15.

3.2 DISCUSSIONS

The performance evaluation of the integrated double exposure box-type solar cookers demonstrates both the potentials and limitations of thermal storage in solar cooking systems. The stagnation tests conducted under controlled conditions reveal that both cookers, when operated without phase change materials (PCMs), attained high absorber plate temperatures of 151 °C and 150 °C, respectively. These values align with the findings of Loff (2005), who reported comparable stagnation temperatures for conventional solar box cookers. They also surpass the 110–115 °C range reported by Rekha et al. (2018) for baking applications, indicating that the dual-exposure design effectively enhances heat capture through its combined use of plane mirrors and a parabolic reflector. The resulting first figure of merit (F1) of 0.18 places the system in the Grade B category, as classified by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS), confirming its adequacy for cooking applications but also highlighting room for improvement in thermal efficiency.

When integrated with PCMs, specifically shea butter oil and cow fat, the thermal behavior of the cookers changed significantly. The maximum temperatures decreased to 133 °C for shea butter and 136 °C for cow fat, with corresponding F1 values of 0.15 and 0.16, respectively. This reduction is consistent with Sharma (2000) and Saxena et al. (2020), who noted that the incorporation of PCMs results in a redistribution of absorbed heat: part of the energy is diverted into melting the storage medium rather than being available for immediate temperature rise. However, this trade-off is beneficial for practical cooking needs because it enables extended usability of the cooker during periods of low or no insolation. The observed thermal plateaus in both shea butter and cow fat around their melting ranges (50–69 °C) confirm their capacity to absorb latent heat, store energy, and subsequently release it in a controlled manner, thereby maintaining the cooking chamber temperature for longer durations.

Comparing the two PCMs, cow fat demonstrated slightly better performance with higher stagnation temperature and figure of merit than shea butter. This suggests that cow fat, with a lower melting temperature, may have a higher thermal responsiveness under field conditions in Sokoto's climatic

environment. Nonetheless, both materials proved viable and advantageous due to their local availability, non-toxicity, and low cost compared to imported or synthetic PCMs like paraffin waxes and salt hydrates, which are often criticized for their cost and environmental hazards (Omara et al., 2020; Cuce et al., 2013). This aligns with the sustainability goal of promoting locally sourced materials in renewable energy systems.

The role of environmental parameters was also evident throughout the experiments. Solar irradiance peaked at 900–910 W/m², consistent with tropical solar potential, while ambient temperatures averaged 33–34 °C. Wind speed was shown to exert a strong influence on cooker performance; at 0.2 m/s, maximum plate temperatures were attained, whereas an increase to 2.1 m/s caused a sharp temperature drop of approximately 10 °C due to convective losses. This finding corroborates Sharma (2000), who emphasized wind as a dominant heat loss pathway in outdoor cooker performance. Consequently, design modifications such as improved insulation and streamlined glazing may further minimize convective losses and raise effective thermal efficiency.

The experimental outcomes also underscore the advantages of the double exposure configuration. Unlike conventional single-glass box cookers, this design allows the absorber plate to receive radiation from both the upper and lower surfaces, effectively doubling the heat input. This accounts for the high initial stagnation temperatures and positions the cookers as a promising step toward efficient, low-cost cooking solutions for rural communities. While the inclusion of PCM lowered the peak temperature, it also extended the cooking window by reducing temperature fluctuations, thus enhancing reliability for evening cooking a major drawback of traditional solar cookers.

Overall, the study demonstrates that integrating simple, locally fabricated thermal storage units with indigenous PCMs into double exposure solar cookers yields a practical and sustainable technology. Though categorized as Grade B systems by BIS standards, their demonstrated performance indicates that with incremental refinements, particularly in insulation, glazing optimization, and PCM encapsulation, the cookers can transition toward Grade A classification. This would make them not only competitive with traditional fuels in rural households but also scalable for institutional cooking. Furthermore, the study contributes to expanding the knowledge base on alternative PCM candidates by validating shea butter and cow fat as effective, safe, and affordable thermal storage media.

Table 2: Summary of the Thermal Performance Test

SN	Type of Cooker	Figure of Merit	Max. Plate Temperature Attained (°C)	Max Irradiance (W/m ²)	Wind Speed Range (m/s)	Max Ambient Temperature (°C)
1	Cooker A Unloaded	0.18	151 (°C)	900 (W/m ²)	0.2 – 2.1	31.5
2	Cooker B Unloaded	0.18	150 (°C)	900 (W/m ²)	0.2 – 2.1	31.5
3	Cooker with Shea butter	0.15	133 (°C)	910 (W/m ²)	0.2 – 2.1	34.0
4	Cooker with fat	0.16	136 (°C)	910 (W/m ²)	0.2 – 2.1	34.0

CONCLUSION

This study successfully developed and evaluated two identical double exposure box-type solar cookers integrated with locally sourced phase change materials (PCMs) shea butter oil and cow fat. The results showed that under stagnation conditions without storage media, both cookers achieved high absorber plate temperatures of 150–151 °C with a figure of merit (F1) of 0.18, placing them in the Grade B category according to BIS standards. When PCMs were incorporated, maximum plate temperatures decreased slightly to 133 °C and 136 °C, with F1 values of 0.15 and 0.16 for shea butter and cow fat respectively. This reduction reflects the diversion of heat into latent storage, but it also highlights the

advantage of extended heat retention and prolonged cooking potential during periods of reduced or no sunlight. Between the two PCMs, cow fat exhibited marginally better performance, though both proved effective, safe, and sustainable.

The findings confirm that double exposure solar cookers integrated with indigenous PCMs can provide a cost-effective, environmentally friendly, and practical cooking alternative for communities in sun-rich regions like northern Nigeria. The use of locally available materials not only reduces production costs but also enhances the prospects for community acceptance and large-scale adoption. However, further refinements such as improved insulation, better glazing systems, and optimized PCM encapsulation are recommended to enhance thermal efficiency and potentially achieve Grade A performance. Overall, this work demonstrates the viability of combining innovative cooker design with affordable local storage media as a pathway toward sustainable energy solutions and reduced dependence on fossil fuels.

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NOMENCLATURE

- G_s = Global solar radiation (W/m^2)
 WS = Wind speed (m/s)
 A = Aperture area (m^2)
 T_A = Ambient temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
 F_1 = First figure of merit
 F_2 = Second figure of merit
 T_{w1} = Initial water temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
 T_{w2} = Final water temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
 $(Mc)_w$ = Product of mass of water and specific heat (J/k)
 (t_2-t_1) = Time taken to heat the water from T_{w1} to T_{w2} (seconds)
 SBT = Shea butter temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
 CFT = Cow fat temperature ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TOAA$ = Oven air temperature for cooker A ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TOAB$ = Oven air temperature for cooker B ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TPAA$ = Absorber plate temperature for Cooker A ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TPAB$ = Absorber plate temperature for Cooker B ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TPACF$ = Absorber plate temperature for Cow fat cooker ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TPASB$ = Absorber plate temperature for Shea butter cooker A ($^{\circ}C$)
 GS = Global solar radiation (W/m^2)
 TGA = Glass temperature of cooker A ($^{\circ}C$)
 TGB = Glass temperature of cooker B ($^{\circ}C$)
 WS = Wind speed (m/s)
 $TGSB$ = Glass temperature for shea butter cooker ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TPASB$ = Absorber plate temperature for shea butter cooker ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TPACF$ = Absorber plate temperature for cow fat cooker ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TOASB$ = Oven air temperature for shea butter cooker ($^{\circ}C$)
 $TOACF$ = Oven air temperature for cow fat cooker ($^{\circ}C$)
 MDF = Medium density fibre
 PCM = Phase change material
 TES = Thermal energy storage
 $DEBSC$ = Double exposure box type solar cooker
 $LHTES$ = Latent heat thermal energy storage
 $HSMs$ = Heat storage materials
 SHS = Sensible heat storage
 $BTSC$ = Box type solar cooker